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ASSESSMENT OF PATIENT PERCEPTION ABOUT GENERIC VS BRANDED MEDICINES PRESCRIBED IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: A generic medicine contains the same active substance(s) as the reference medicine, and it is used at the same dose(s) to treat the same disease(s) as the reference medicine. However, the name of the medicine, its appearance (such as colour or shape) and its packaging can be different from those of the reference medicine'. However, all agree on the general requirements that the product is off-patent, contains an active ingredient in a previously approved medicine, is shown to be bioequivalent to that previously approved medicine, and has the same dosage form, route of administration and treatment characteristics. **MATERIALS AND METHODS:** A prospective observational study was carried out over a period of six months in General Medicine Department Of Muthoot Healthcare, Pvt. Ltd, Kozhencherry. The type 2 diabetic patients who were on oral hypoglycemic were enrolled in the study. The knowledge of the patients was assessed by using a set of questionnaire. For this study 398 subjects were enrolled based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. **RESULTS:** Out of 398 subjects, 292 subjects (74.4%) have not heard about generic medicines and the perception of patients regarding generic medicines were poor.

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INTRODUCTION

Generic drugs are the copies of branded drugs. Generic medicines have the same quality, safety, and efficacy as their counterpart original branded medicines. In other words, their pharmacological effects are exactly the same as those of their brand-name counterpart.^[1] Generic medicines provide the same therapeutic outcomes but at a much cheaper cost, so are promoted in many countries to contain pharmaceutical expenditure and sustain the health care system. Thus, the perspective of patients and medicine consumers as end users of these medicines is an important factor to enhance the use and utilization of generic medicines. When a company brings a new drug onto the market, the firm has already spent substantial money on research, development, marketing and promotion of the drug. A patent is granted that gives the company that developed the drug an exclusive right to sell the drug as long as the patent is in effect.^[2]

As the patent nears expiration, manufacturers can apply to the FDA for permission to make and sell generic versions of the drug; and without the start up costs for development of the drug, other companies can afford to make and sell it more cheaply. When multiple companies begin producing and selling a drug, the competition among them can also drive the price down even further. So there's no truth in the myths that generic drugs are manufactured in poorer-quality facilities or are inferior in quality to brand-name drugs. The FDA applies the same standards for all drug manufacturing facilities, and many companies manufacture both brand-name and generic drugs. In fact, the FDA estimates that 50% of generic drug production is by brand-name companies.^[3]

Another common misbelief is that generic drugs take longer to work. The FDA requires that generic drugs work as fast and as effectively as the original brand-name products. Sometimes, generic versions of a drug have different colors, flavors, or combinations of inactive ingredients than the original medications. Trademark laws in the United States do not allow the generic drugs to look exactly like the brand-name preparation, but the active ingredients must be the same in both preparations, ensuring that both have the same medicinal effect.^[4,5]

With a few exceptions, e.g. Ireland and the UK, generic drug use has been promoted in western countries by allowing pharmacists to substitute drugs defined as therapeutically equivalent generics. Although this enables cost savings, which can slow growing pharmaceutical budgets, concerns have been raised regarding the possibility of such substitution leading to a higher overall healthcare expenditure. The core of these concerns is that problems may arise when a brand-name drug, with which the patient is familiar, is replaced by a product with a different name and with other physical attributes, e.g. shape, size, and colour. Currently, patients with chronic medical conditions are increasingly affected by substitution reforms because they consume more drugs over a longer period of time and the generics interchangeable markets are expanding in response to policy changes and expiration of patents.^[4]

The use of generic drugs can provide substantial savings in health care cost without affecting the quality or the therapeutic effect of the prescribed medicine. A generic drug is identical, or bioequivalent, to a brand name drug in dosage form, safety, strength, route of administration, quality, performance characteristics and intended use.^[5]

The adoption of generic drugs in medical practices is a complex phenomenon and many determinants can affect it. Physicians play a key role in controlling this phenomenon and their decision in prescribing generic drugs is likely to be affected by many factors. Although there is increasing local and international encouragement for physicians to prescribe generic products, some physicians are not in favour of prescribing generic drugs.^[6]

The use of generic drugs is steadily increasing internationally as a result of economic pressure on drug budgets. Generic drugs provide the opportunity for major savings in healthcare expenditure since they are usually substantially lower in price than the innovator brands. However, physicians are apprehensive regarding the quality of generic drugs and have concerns about their reliability as well as interchange of certain drug categories. Although the generic medicines are bio equivalents of their innovator counterparts and are produced in similar facilities according to good manufacturing practices, these are widely believed as inferior in their therapeutic efficacy and quality to branded products.^[6]

Marketing practices adopted by manufacturers of imported branded medicines also propagate the belief that generics are of inferior quality as reported from countries in Central and Eastern Europe and independent countries emerged from the former Soviet Union.^[7]

Currently, almost all medicines in India are sold under a brand (trade) name and medicines are called branded medicines or branded-generic. In real sense, Indian market does not have branded medicines (a name commonly given to an innovator product) because till January 2005 product patents were not applicable in India. In India, many pharmaceutical companies manufacture two types of products for the same molecule, i.e. the branded product which they advertise and push through doctors and branded-generic which they expect retailers to push in the market.^[16,17] The so-called branded medicines in India are manufactured and promoted by multinationals or by reputed Indian manufacturers. Branded-generics, on the other hand, are not promoted or advertised by the manufacturer. This category closely resembles formulations referred to as 'generics' worldwide. Patients' and doctors' perception for all branded-generics irrespective of company is the same. In India, generic substitution is legally not allowed so patients' awareness about generics is limited and doctors and patients do not want pharmacists to change the trade name written by doctors. Hence, consumer awareness for the generics, variety of trade names available in the market, and price variation is very limited. Hence, there is a need to conduct a study that can document the price structure and quality of the branded product and their branded-generic versions manufactured in India. Since 2012, the Government of India, has initiated exclusive generic drug outlets called Jan Aushadhi stores.^[8]

Our country has become competent enough to produce quality branded and generic medicines. Pharmaceutical industry has become a giant compared to any other industry. Data suggests that the pharma industry increased to 1,19,000 crores in 2012 from 1,500 crores in 1980. However, these medicines are reasonably priced, as compared to the developed countries. Still, a large population which belongs to a marginalized category in our country cannot afford these branded medicines. Accordingly, ensuring availability of quality medicines at affordable prices to all, has been a key objective of the Indian government.^[9]

AIM OF THE STUDY:

The aim of this study is to evaluate the patient perception regarding generic and branded medicines.

ETHICAL APPROVAL:

This study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee in a tertiary care hospital.

METHODOLOGY:

A Prospective Observational Study was conducted at the General Medicine Department of MUTHOOT HEALTHCARE, Pvt. Ltd, KOZHENCHERRY for a period of 6 months (November 2018- May 2019) with a sample size of 398 patients. The sample size was calculated using standard statistical formulas.

Inclusion criteria

Patients under the General Medicine Department.

Exclusion Criteria

- Pregnant ladies
- Pediatric Population
- Patients with incomplete data
- Patients who are not co-operative.

PROCEDURE

A set of validated questionnaires was used to collect the information after getting consent from the patient.

- Informed consent form
- Validated questionnaires

All the collected data were documented in the pre designed data collection form.

DATA ANALYSIS:

The data was entered in Microsoft Excel 2010 and the results were analyzed as tabular form and percentages.

OBSERVATIONS:

Tableno.1 PATIENT PERCEPTION ABOUT GENERIC AND BRANDED MEDICINES.

SI.NO	QUESTIONNAIRE	YES	NO
1	Do you ever heard about generic medicines?	106	292
2	Do you understand the difference between generic and branded medicine?	51	347
3	Do you know that there is price difference between generic and branded medicine?	49	349
4	If yes,then which is cheaper generic or branded?	49	349
5	Would you prefer buying generic medicines over branded medicines?	46	352
6	Have you ever asked your doctor to prescribe generic medicines?	24	374
7	Have you ever asked the chemist to give you generic medicines in place of branded medicines?	18	381
8	Do you think there is difference in the quality of generic medicine as compared to branded variant?	13	385
9	Do you think there is a difference in the price of generic and branded medicines?	40	358
10	Which type of the medicines whether generic or branded,do you consider should be promoted?	41	357

FIGURE NO.1 PATIENT PERCEPTION ABOUT GENERIC AND BRANDED MEDICINES.

From this figure no:1 we can conclude that the study conducted on 398 subjects, 292(74.4%) have not heard about generic medicines. It also shows that about 347 (88.5%) don't know the difference between them and 347 (88.5%) have no idea regarding generic medicines. In this study, the highest percentage of the patients i.e., about 89.03% of them don't know the fact that generic medicines are cheaper than branded medicines and it shows that only 46 (11.7%) patients out of 398 patients preferred buying generic medicines whereas more than half of the patients i.e., 352 (89.7%) patients don't prefer generic medicines. About 95.4% in this study have not yet requested their physician to prescribe generic medicines.. About 13(3.30%) of the patients have a belief that there is difference in the quality of generic medicines when compared to branded medicines. Highest percentages of the patients (91.3%) are not aware about the price difference between generic and branded medicines and have concluded that 357 (91.3%) patients are not interested to promote generic medicines over branded medicines.

DISCUSSION

Our study concludes that knowledge and attitude about generic medicines among participants were poor. Highest percentages (74.4%) of the patients enrolled in our study have not even heard about generic medicines and don't know the difference between generic and branded medicines. Our study also concluded that most of the patients i.e., more than three-fourth of the total subjects (91.3%) are not interested in promoting the generic medicines over branded medicines. Advertisements and leaflets provided by manufacturing company makes the population more aware about branded medicines while the lack of promotions and campaigns about generic drugs lead to a population who are unaware about the cost effective generic medicines. Andre C *et al.*,^[10] concluded that most of the patients have not heard about generic medicines and don't know the difference between generic and branded medicines. This finding strongly agrees with our study.

CONCLUSION

Out of 398 subjects, 292 subjects (74.4%) have not heard about generic medicines and the perceptions of patients regarding generic medicines were poor.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

NIL

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